

MICROWAVE INDUCED DEGRADATION OF GLASS FIBER REINFORCED POLYESTER FOR FIBER AND RESIN RECOVERY

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ABSTRACT

A solvolysis process to depolymerize the resin in glass fiber reinforced composites and recover the glass fibers has been investigated using microwave induced irradiation. The depolymerization was carried out in HNO₃ with concentrations in the range of 1M-7M and in KOH with concentrations ranging from 1M-3.5M. In case of 3.5 M HNO₃, 100 % resin removal at 208°C and recovery of pristine glass fibers without damage on the surface was achieved. Furthermore, recovery of the monomer phthalic acid was obtained using HNO₃. Decreased level of depolymerization was observed using KOH at concentrations ranging from 1-3.5M. Maximum 63 % resin removal was achieved using 1 M KOH and the resin removal efficiency decreased at higher KOH concentrations (3.5M). The glass fiber surfaces were damaged at both concentrations with more pronounced damages using 3.5M KOH. It was not possible to recover monomers using KOH.

1 INTRODUCTION

Today, glass- and carbon fiber reinforced composites (GFRP/CFRP) is utilized in a multitude of applications, including, containers, wind turbine blades, profiles, boat hulls etc. However, when these units are to be decommissioned there is no direct way of reusing the fibers or the resin of the thermoset, thus waste becomes an issue. Looking at the wind turbine industry there is currently installed 129 GW of capacity (12 GW in 2014 alone) with no expected decrease of the rate of installation [1]. A recent report estimates that the fiber reinforced composite (FRC) waste generated from decommissioning of these turbines will generate up to 10 t/MW installed [2], thus it is of interest to investigate the possibility of detaching fiber and thermoset and reusing both.

Degradation and recycling of FRC has been investigated for a number of years through various approaches. Currently the Danish GenVind Innovation Consortium is investigating the possibility of reuse/recycling of wind turbine blades through various approaches, one of which are presented in the paper.

In general, the main methods involve either mechanical treatment, thermal processes or solvolysis [3]. Mechanical treatment traditionally consists of milling or cutting of the FRC to obtain powders or flakes of resin and fibers embedded in resin which may be used as fillers or incinerated for energy gains. Of more interest in a recycling perspective are the thermal processes and solvolysis methods since these are methods for separating fiber and resin. Although different methods both still require initial mechanical treatment due to space limitations of reactors for these processes. The thermal processes utilizes high temperature processes such as pyrolysis for degradation of the resin but due to high temperatures a decrease in mechanical properties of the fibers are generally observed, although in some cases losses of as little as 2-5 % of tensile strength has been found [3,4]. Solvolysis, the use of chemicals to degrade the FRC, has proven to yield fibers with losses in mechanical properties less than the thermal methods [3]. Several reaction medias, such as water [5-9], methanol [10,11], propanol [11,12] and others has been proven applicable for the degradation of FRC. Not only fibers may be recovered as useful products of these degradation methods, but also the resin itself may be degraded to

useful components such as pyrolysis oil in case of thermals methods [3,4]. Using solvolysis methods polyester resins has been degraded to yield monomers that could be polymerized into a polymer with mechanical properties resembling the virgin material [13]. In general, although the monomers or similar components may be obtained from the solvolysis of the resin, it tends to form a complex mixture, which requires significant efforts of separation to acquire the pure components.

The work described in this paper is using different solvents and microwave heating, which in itself has been shown to be successful on CFRC by Lester et.al. [14], to separate fibers and resin in polyester GFRC and recover fibers and chemicals for reuse/recycling.

2 MATERIALS & METHODS

The matrix of the glass fiber reinforced composite (GFRP) materials used in this paper was unsaturated polyester resin (UP). The UP resin prepolymer was made from maleic anhydride, phthalic anhydride and propylene glycol, which was cross-linked with styrene (Fig. 1). The resin content, evaluated by calcination following the recommendation of the standard DS/EN ISO 1172 was 27.15 wt. % \pm 0.2 wt. % based on the average of the value measured on three samples. Acetone (ACS reagent grade with a purity of 99.5 %) was purchased from Aldrich Denmark. Potassium hydroxide (KOH) pellets were purchased from AppliChem Germany. The water applied in the recycling process was demineralized water and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) was purchased from VWR chemicals.

Figure 1. Structure of polystyrene cured UP resin

2.1 Microwave induced degradation

Degradation of GFRP was conducted in an Anton Paar Microwave Pro 1400 W. In brief, each catalyst was prepared individually and mixed together before transferring the solution into a rotor with 8 XF100 teflon vessels. The vessels were placed in the microwave reactor and heated using 900 W to temperatures between 173 °C – 239 °C and 60 bar for 30 min. Experiments were conducted according to Table 1. Heating to 173 °C – 239 °C and cooling to ambient conditions was in both cases 30 min.

Subsequent treatment in the microwave reactor, the glass fibers were washed with demineralized water to remove residual KOH from the fiber surfaces and with acetone to remove organic residue. The efficiency of the microwave irradiation process and the solvent/catalyst blends, in terms of resin degradation, was evaluated according to degraded resin from the surface of the fibers (equation 1).

$$\text{Degraded resin (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Weight of composite} - \text{weight of solid residue}}{\text{Weight of resin in composite}} \right) \cdot 100\% \quad (1)$$

Run	Temp. (°C)	Solvent/catalyst blends				Total volume of water + Catalyst (ml)	Initial mass of composite (g)	Composite (g)/Solvent ratio (ml)
		KOH	H ₂ O ₂	Acetone	HNO ₃			
1	230	1 M				10	2.62	0.26
2	239	3.5 M				10	2.55	0.26
3	212	0.4 M	1.5 v/v %	13 v/v %		20	5.77	0.29
4	207			50 v/v %		30	4.27	0.14
5	198	0.4 M		50 v/v %		30	4.93	0.16
6	207	1.4 M		50 v/v %		30	5.96	0.20
7	220				1 M	30	3.30	0.11
8	207				2 M	15	2.44	0.16
9	208				3.5 M	30	4.61	0.15
10	173				7 M	30	4.97	0.17

Table 1. Design of experiments. All the dilutions were prepared using demineralized water.

2.2 Analysis of degradation products using GC-MS

The degradation products produced by treatment in the microwave reactor were characterized using a Perkin Elmer Clarus Model 500 gas chromatograph coupled with a Perkin Elmer Clarus Model 500 quadrupole mass spectrometer (GC-MS). The analytical column was an Elite-5 fused silica capillary column (30 m × 0.25 mm inner diameter (ID) with 0.10 μm film thickness). The initial column temperature of the GC was 75 °C for 1.5 min, followed by increasing the temperature linearly to 275 °C at a rate of 20 °C/min. The temperature was held at 275 °C for 10.5 min. The flow rate of the carrier gas (helium) was maintained at 1.0 mL/min. All MS analyses were conducted in scan mode (mass range of 75-600 amu) with electron impact ionization (EI) of 70 eV. A Perkin Elmer Clarus Model 500 autosampler was used to inject samples into the GC with an injection volume of V_{inj} 1.0 μL.

Sample preparation prior to the GC-MS investigations was performed as follows: The reaction solution was evaporated by natural convection. The residue was redissolved in 6 mL acetone, which was filtered using a 40 μm filter and subsequently analyzed directly by GC-MS. Since the reaction solution from experiment 6 contained two phases (water phase at the bottom, organic phase at the top) subsequent the microwave treatment, these phases were initially separated using a separation funnel and prepared similarly as the other samples.

Degradation products were identified by comparison of spectral data with that in the NIST library. The area of peaks, corresponding to degradation products, was calculated using the GC-MS software to predict product selectivity.

2.3 Analysis of degradation products using FT-IR

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) analyses were conducted on both the acetone soluble residue and the none-acetone soluble residue obtained after evaporation of the reaction solution. Acquisition of FT-IR spectra were carried out using a Thermo Fisher Nicolet iS5 FT-IR spectrometer with an ID7 ATR. The software OMNIC version 7 was used for spectra acquisition. The spectra were recorded in absorbance mode with 32 scans at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ in the range of 525–4000 cm⁻¹. The FT-IR results presented in the paper is based on the average of the values measured on three scans.

2.4 SEM-EDS analysis of recovered glass fibers

Scanning electron microscopy with energy dispersive spectroscopy (SEM-EDS) analysis of the recovered glass fibers was performed using a Philips XL30 ESEM-FEG. The recovered glass fibers samples were prior to investigation coated with a thin layer of gold to make the samples conducting.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Resin degradation efficiency

Fig.2 shows the percentage degraded resin achieved after treatment in a microwave reactor using different solvent/catalyst blends at temperatures in the range of 173 °C – 239 °C. Highest resin elimination was achieved using 3.5M HNO₃, followed by the other experiments conducted using HNO₃. Significant differences were observed between the experiments conducted with HNO₃, indicating that concentration and temperature influence the efficiency of resin degradation.

Figure 2. Percentage degraded resin using different solvent/catalyst blends at temperatures ranging from 173 °C – 239 °C (Table 1)

Similar degradation efficiencies was observed for experiment 7 (1 M HNO₃) and 10 (7 M HNO₃), emphasizing both the effect of concentration and temperature, since the temperature was 220 °C and 173 °C, respectively. The effect of the HNO₃ concentration is observed when comparing experiment 8 and 9. Increasing the concentration from 2 M to 3.5 M resulted in 29 % higher resin elimination.

The experiments with the catalysts acetone, KOH and H₂O₂ exhibited decreased degradation efficiencies compared to the experiments conducted with HNO₃. Highest resin degradation efficiencies within these experiments (1-6) was achieved in experiment 1 (1 M KOH), experiment 2 (3.5 M KOH) and experiment 6 (1.4 M KOH/acetone), indicating that KOH enhances the resin degradation efficiency. However, high KOH concentrations (3.5 M) seems to have a negative effect upon resin degradation, as the percentage degraded resin decreased compared to the experiment with 1 M KOH. Addition of H₂O₂ (experiment 3) and acetone (experiment 4) exhibited lowest degradation efficiencies.

3.2 GC-MS investigations of degradation products

Results from the GC-MS analysis are presented in Fig. 3. Fig. 3a presents the chromatograms from experiment 4-6. GC-MS investigations from experiments 1-3 and the water phase obtained from experiment 6 are not included, as no degradation products were observed. In Fig. 2, it is observed that up to 63 % resin degradation was achieved in these experiments, indicating that the resin has been degraded into degradation products with high molecular weights, which cannot be identified using GC-MS.

Figure 3. GC-MS chromatograms of the acetone soluble degradation products obtained by degradation of UP resin using a microwave reactor in water with the additives: Acetone, H₂O₂, KOH and HNO₃ for a) experiment 4-6 and b) experiment 7-10.

Peak assignment	RT (min)	Compound	Portion of total chromatographic peak area (x 10 ⁸)							
			# 4	# 5	# 6	# 7	# 8	# 9	# 10	
1	3.99	Isophorone		108	409					
-	4.13	4-Methylpent-3-en-2-one		-	5.1					
2	4.41	Benzoic acid	9.3	7.4	-	393	204	90.8	6.6	
3	5.52	Phthalic acid	562	-	-	196	74.5	88.6	13.8	
4	5.74	2-PTCY		83	339					
5	5.86	2-CHTP		76	297					
6	6.22	3-Carene, 4-acetyl		44	121					
7	6.80	2H-CBHTM		210	724					
8	7.24	o-Nitrobenzoic acid			-			10.9		
9	7.28	2H-NDTM		650	1550					
10	9.02	7-AETM		221	1060					
11	10.83	1-AHPE		7.7	64					

Table 2. Show the distribution of most abundant degradation compounds in each experiment. Abbreviations: (2-PTCY): 2-Propanone,1-(3,5,5-trimethyl-2-cyclohexen-1-ylidene), (2-CHTP): 2-Cyclohexen-1-one,3,5,5-trimethyl-2-(2-propenyl), (2H-CBHTM): 2H-Cyclopropa[g]benzofuran, 4,5,5a,6,6a,6b-hexahydro-4,4,6b-trimethyl-2-(1-methylethenyl), (2H-NDTM): 1(2H)-Naphthalenone, 3,4-dihydro-3,3,6,8-tetramethyl, (7-AETM): 7-Acetyl-6-ethyl-1,1,4,4-tetramethyltetralin, (1-AHPE): 1-{4-[6-(4-Acetylphenyl)hexyl]phenyl}ethanone

Experiment 4 was the experiment with addition of acetone in water. The most intense peak (**3**) in this chromatogram is assigned as phthalic acid, which is one of the monomers in the UP resin degraded in this study. The other degradation product identified in this experiment was benzoic acid, which is a degradation product of phthalic acid, explaining the presence of the compound. Recovery of phthalic acid was not achieved in experiment 5 and 6. In addition to experiment 4 with only acetone added, KOH was also added in experiment 5 (0.4 M) and 6 (1.4 M). This indicates that addition of KOH might degrade phthalic acid into other degradation products. The chromatograms from experiment 5 and 6 contain significantly more peaks with higher intensities than in the absence of

KOH. Identification of the peaks revealed compounds derived from aldol-reactions of acetone (Fig. 4) and not degradation products from the resin. The assignment and the area of the peaks are given in Table 2. The production routes for the most abundant compounds in experiment 5 and 6 are presented in Fig. 4. Compounds produced by two to five acetone moieties were observed, producing compounds with higher molecular weights, which are not soluble in water. This explains the formation of a water phase (lower phase) and an organic phase (upper phase) in experiment 6. However, the reaction solution from experiment 5 was not separated into two phases. This indicates lower quantities of the acetone derived compounds as a consequence of the lower concentration of KOH. This can also be observed based on the area of the peaks on Table 2. The productions of these compounds are therefore highly catalyzed by KOH and exclusively produced by the presence of KOH in acetone.

The experiments conducted with HNO_3 (experiment 7-10) are similar to each other in terms of degradation products. Phthalic acid (**3**) and benzoic acid (**2**) were identified in all the experiments.

Figure 4. Production route of most abundant degradation compounds from acetone aldol reactions found in experiment 5 and 6.

3.3 FT-IR investigations

Based on the GC-MS investigations (section 3.2), it was not possible to obtain UP resin degradation products from experiment 1-3 and experiment 6, despite 26 % - 56 % resin elimination. FT-IR analysis was therefore conducted on the dried residue from experiment 1-3 and experiment 5-10, primarily to provide greater knowledge about the none-acetone soluble degradation products.

FT-IR spectra of the degradation products from the HNO_3 experiments are shown in Fig. 5. The first part of the spectra ($3000\text{-}2000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) shows a broad peak assigned as the stretching vibrations of OH from carboxylic acids (COOH). This indicates the presence of benzoic acid and phthalic acid, as identified in the GC-MS investigations. The peak around 1675 cm^{-1} corresponds to the C=O group in carboxylic acids (1689 cm^{-1} assigned to benzoic acid and 1678 cm^{-1} assigned to phthalic acid) [1]. This reveals important knowledge about the nature of the degradation products, as the presence of phthalic acid instead of phthalic anhydride is confirmed due to the missing peaks at $1700\text{-}1780\text{ cm}^{-1}$, corresponding to C=O groups of anhydrides [1].

The peaks at 1530 cm^{-1} and 1345 cm^{-1} are assigned as asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of NO_2 substituted benzene rings [2]. This indicates that nitration of benzoic acid has occurred throughout all the HNO_3 experiments and not only in experiment 9. However, the intensities of these peaks appear to be higher in experiment 9 and experiment 10, indicating higher quantities of nitrated benzoic acid. The wavenumbers at 1321 cm^{-1} , 1178 cm^{-1} , 1126 cm^{-1} , 1026 cm^{-1} and 683 cm^{-1} seems to have decreased in intensity in the experiments with HNO_2 concentrations from 2M-7M compared to the experiment with 1M. This indicates degradation of benzoic acid, since these bands are characteristic for benzoic acid [1]. Furthermore, the peaks with wavenumbers of 705 cm^{-1} and 666 cm^{-1} (corresponding to characteristic bands of benzoic acid) in the experiment with 1M HNO_3 were shifted to higher wavenumbers corresponding to 716 cm^{-1} and 672 cm^{-1} in the experiments from 2M-7M HNO_3 . The wavenumbers 716 cm^{-1} and 672 cm^{-1} are assignable to the twisting mode of NO_2 groups, once again indicating nitration of benzoic acid.

Based on the GC-MS investigations, nitrated benzoic acid was only identified in the experiment with 3.5M HNO_3 . However, considering the interpretations of the FT-IR spectra, nitro compounds might also be present in the experiments with 2M and 7M HNO_3 .

Figure 5. FT-IR spectra obtained from dried residue from experiment 7-10. The residue from all the experiments was soluble in acetone.

Figure 6. Comparison of FT-IR spectra conducted on dry residue from experiment 1-2. The residue from both experiments was not soluble in acetone.

From comparison of the spectra in Fig. 6, it can be observed that the residue from experiment 1 and experiment 2 contain KOH, but also degraded UP resin. The first part of the spectra exhibits a wide broad peak corresponding to the stretching vibrations of OH, which might originate primarily from the KOH. The peak around 1366 cm^{-1} , 1066 cm^{-1} and 702 cm^{-1} are also originating from the KOH present in the residue. However, the peak at 1674 cm^{-1} , 1560 cm^{-1} and 1274 cm^{-1} originates exclusively from the degraded resin. The peak around 1560 cm^{-1} is assigned to C=C stretching vibrations of aromatic rings and observed in both experiments due to the polystyrene groups and phthalic anhydride groups. The peak at 1674 cm^{-1} and 1274 cm^{-1} were only present in the experiment with 3.5M KOH, indicating the presence of different degradation products than in experiment 1 (1M KOH). The peak at 1674 cm^{-1} are considered assigned to the C=O stretching vibrations of a ketone conjugated with a benzene ring. This indicates cleavage of C-O bonds between phthalic anhydride and propylene glycol to produce aromatic ketone functional groups. The peak at 1274 cm^{-1} is assigned to C-O stretching vibrations, possible from the ester groups between phthalic anhydride and propylene glycol moieties.

IR spectra for the experiments with KOH, H_2O_2 and acetone are presented on Fig. 7. The spectra obtained for the organic phase (OP) in experiment 6 were significantly different from spectra of the other experiments, which were more similar to each other. The most predominant differences were the absence of the wide band in the region $3000\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the presence of the peak at 1666 cm^{-1} . The absence of the wide band in the hydroxyl region is possibly related to the absence of KOH. KOH is insoluble in acetone and possibly also in the majority of acetone derivatives produced, and will tend to stay in the water phase. The peak at 1666 cm^{-1} corresponds to C=O stretching vibrations of aromatic ketones. This observation is consistent with the results obtained in the GC-MS investigations, where a range of aromatic ketones were identified. The intense peak at 1558 cm^{-1} assigned as the stretching vibrations of aromatic C=C rings was present in FTIR spectra from the results of experiment 3, 5 and 6 (water phase) and with high intensity, similarly as in experiment 1 and 2. The intense peak around 1373 cm^{-1} was assigned to KOH in the residue.

Figure 7. Comparison of FT-IR spectra conducted on dry residue from experiment 3-6. The residue from experiment 3 and 6 (water phase) was not soluble in acetone. Experiment 5 was not completely soluble in acetone and experiment 6 was completely soluble in acetone. Abbreviations: AC: Acetone, OP: Organic phase, WP: Water phase.

Despite the absence of UP resin degradation products throughout experiment 1-3 and experiment 6 in the GC-MS investigations, it was possible to demonstrate the presence of degradation products originating from the UP resin by using FT-IR.

3.4 SEM-EDS analysis of recovered glass fibers

SEM images of recovered glass fibers from microwave assisted hydrothermal degradation of glass fiber-reinforced polyester composite materials under different conditions are shown in Fig. 8. Comparison of the SEM images show that degradation of the GRP composite material under acidic condition (run 7 and 9) results in recovery of almost pristine glass fibers without visible surface changes or damage to the fibers. EDS analysis of the recovered glass fibers shows that fibers washed with distilled water contains small amounts of residual carbon on the surface. Fibers subject to an additional acetone-washing step showed a significant reduction in the amount of residual carbon on the glass fiber surface.

In comparison SEM images of glass fibers recovered after hydrothermal treatment of the composite material under basic conditions (run 1 and 2) show that the glass fibers are damaged and not completely separated from the resin. The recovered glass fibers show sign of surface etching for both the 1 and 3.5 M concentration of KOH, even though it is more pronounced in the case of the 3.5 M KOH (Fig. 8e). EDS analysis of the surface of the recovered fibers (Fig. 8f) suggest that the residue covering the fibers partly consist of undissolved resin, precipitated potassium hydroxide and Zeolite formed from dissolution of the glass fiber during treatment. The increase in damage observed for the glass fibers recovered after treatment at high pH correspond to the higher solubility of silicon materials at high pH.

Figure 8. SEM images of a) virgin glass fibers, b) recovered glass fibers (1 M HNO₃), c) Acetone washed glass fibers (1 M HNO₃), d) Acetone washed glass fibers (3.5 M HNO₃), e) Acetone washed glass fibers (1 M KOH) and f) Acetone washed glass fibers (3.5 M KOH)

9 CONCLUSION

Depolymerization of GFRP composites using microwave irradiation in 3.5M HNO₃ achieved 100 % resin removal at 208 °C and also provide recovered pristine glass fibers without visible surface changes or damage to the fibers. Furthermore, recovery of the monomer phthalic acid was achieved in all the experiments performed with HNO₃.

Similar degree of depolymerization was not achieved using KOH/water, as maximum 63 % resin removal was achieved when the KOH concentration was 1M. The recovered glass fibers were damaged and showed sign of surface etching, as a consequence of the alkaline environments. Increase in KOH concentration to 3.5 M resulted in decreased resin removal (52 %) and more pronounced damage on the surface of the fibers.

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